

Received: 5th January 2022

Revised: 19th January 2022

Accepted: 10th February 2022

COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF THERMAL AND EMISSION CHARACTERISTICS OF EXTRACTED BIODIESEL FROM WASTE COOKING COTTON SEED OIL AND WASTE PALM COOKING OIL BLENDED WITH DIESEL**PRAKASHKUMAR PRAJAPATI AND SADANAND NAMJOSHI****ABSTRACT**

Biodiesel is an alternative and renewable diesel fuel, can be produced from diverse kinds of vegetable oils. The waste cotton seed oil and waste palm oil biodiesel effects on engine performance and emissions vary as the source of oil changes. In this study, waste cotton seed oil biodiesel (WCOB), and Waste Palm oil biodiesel (WPOB) were extracted using transesterification technique and blended with conventional diesel fuel (CDF) in volumetric blending ratios of 10% and 20%. Tests were carried out under electric loads of 0, 3, 6, 9, 12 KW at constant speed of 1500 RPM with Constant Compression ratio 18. Evaluation of engine performance and emission characteristics against constant speed and varying load using a Single cylinder compression ignition engine. The present work shows the better results are better in case of blended waste cotton seed cooking oil compare to blended waste palm cooking oil or mixture of blended cotton seed cooking oil and waste palm cooking in same proportion.

Keywords: Waste cotton seed oil biodiesel, Waste palm oil biodiesel, Performance, Emissions

INTRODUCTION

The results of investigation show increase in brake power and brake thermal efficiency with load for all prepared test fuels that brake thermal efficiency increases with the percentage of additive in all the test fuels. The brake specific fuel consumption decreases with increase in additive percentage. Exhaust gas temperature increases almost linearly with load for all test fuels and decreases with increase in additive percentage. It is also seen from the results that both CO and HC emissions tend to decrease with increase in additive biodiesel. The smoke and NO_x emissions also decrease with increase in additive percentage in the biodiesel fuel.[1] In this article review find increase in global energy demand, consumption of depletable fossil fuels, exhaust emissions and global warming, all these led to search about alternative fuels. Biodiesel was produced from waste cooking-oil by transesterification process. Blends of waste cooking-oil biodiesel and diesel oil were prepared in volume percentages of 10, 20 and 30% as B10, B20 and B30. Biodiesel blends have ASTM standards of physical and chemical characterization near to diesel fuel. Diesel engine performance and exhaust emissions were studied experimentally for burning waste cooking-oil blend with diesel fuel. This experimental was applied on a diesel engine at different engine loads from zero to full load. Thermal efficiencies for waste cooking-oil biodiesel blends were lower than diesel oil. Specific fuel consumptions of biodiesel blends were higher than diesel fuel. Higher exhaust gas temperatures were recorded for biodiesel blends compared to diesel oil. CO₂ emissions for waste cooking-oil biodiesel blends were higher than diesel oil. CO, smoke opacity and HC emissions for biodiesel blends were lower than diesel fuel. NO_x emissions for biodiesel blends were higher than diesel fuel.[2] The use of waste cooking oil such as palm and coconut oil in diesel engines is more sustainable if they can perform similarly to ordinary diesel fuel (B0). the experimental study carried out to evaluate emission and performance characteristics of a multi-cylinder diesel engine operating on waste cooking oil such as 5% palm oil with 95% ordinary diesel fuel (P5) and 5% coconut oil with 95% ordinary diesel fuel (C5). B0 was used for comparison purposes. The results show that there are reductions in brake power of 1.2% and 0.7% for P5 and C5 respectively compared with B0. In addition, reduction of exhaust emissions such as unburned hydrocarbon (HC), smoke, carbon mono-oxide (CO), and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) is offered by the blended fuels and also palm and coconut oil do not have a negative effect on engine performance.[3] the study focused on effect of temperature and component concentration on phase stability of diesel–cotton oil–n-butanol ternary blends. Ternary blend of 70% diesel fuel, 20% cotton oil, 10% n-butanol by volume (DCtOnB), which was prepared by the splash-blending method, obtained from titration values at -10 °C temperature was selected for the engine performance and exhaust emission tests. Engine performance test results of DCtOnB showed that average values of brake torque (2.6%), brake power (1.6%), brake thermal efficiency (BTE) (31.2%), brake mean effective pressure (BMEP) (2.3%) and exhaust gas temperature (3.6%) are lower, while brake specific fuel consumption (BSFC) (34.1%) is higher than those of diesel fuel. As for the emissions of the DCtOnB, it was found that carbon monoxide (CO) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions reduced significantly at low engine speeds, whereas oxides of nitrogen (NO_x) and hydrocarbon (HC) emissions increased, when compared to those

of diesel fuel. Taking these facts into account, a blend of 70% diesel fuel, 20% cotton oil and 10% n-butanol was found the most suitable ratio for low temperature behavior due to the satisfactory fuel properties and reduced exhaust emissions. It was observed that DCtOnB is a promising candidate for renewable fuels at the expense of increasing BSFC, NO_x and HC emissions.[4] Biodiesel is considered as a renewable fuel and an alternative to petro diesel which is derived from transesterification of vegetable oils, the values of the major factors affecting the transesterification of sunflower oil were optimized by the response surface methodology. The experiments were conducted based on central composite rotatable design. Biodiesel was derived from transesterification of sunflower oil with methanol and KOH was used as catalyst. It was assumed that the yield of biodiesel (dependent variable, Y) was mainly affected by the following variables: (1) the molar ratio of methanol to oil, (2) the weight percent of the catalyst, (3) the reaction time and (4) the temperature of the reaction. Using the obtained optimum values of the independent variable, samples of biodiesel were prepared and tested for some common fuel properties, including: flash point, cloud and pour point, kinematic viscosity, copper strip corrosion and ash content Regular diesel fuel and the biodiesel prepared using the optimum values were used in a single cylinder diesel engine for exhaust emission analysis. Most measured fuel properties of optimally produced biodiesel were within the specified range recommended for biodiesel. The emission property test indicated that exhaust emissions of the prepared biodiesel contained lower pollutant than petro diesel.[5] The main objective of the present study is to compare performance, emission and combustion characteristics of biodiesel derived from non edible *Jatropha* oil in a dual fuel diesel engine with base line results of diesel fuel. The different properties of *Jatropha* oil after transesterification were within acceptable limits of standards as set by many countries. The brake thermal efficiency of *Jatropha* methyl ester and its blends with diesel were lower than diesel and brake specific energy consumption was found to be higher. However, HC, CO and CO₂ and smoke were found to be lower with *Jatropha* biodiesel fuel. NO_x emissions on *Jatropha* biodiesel and its blend were higher than Diesel. The results from the experiments suggest that biodiesel derived from non edible oil like *Jatropha* could be a good substitute to diesel fuel in diesel engine in the near future as far as decentralized energy production is concerned. In view of comparable engine performance and reduction in most of the engine emissions, it can be concluded and biodiesel derived from *Jatropha* and its blends could be used in a conventional diesel engine without any modification[6] The use of straight (in modified engines) or blended alcohols with fossil fuel provides an attractive alternative fuel for internal combustion engines A direct-injection compression ignition Perkins diesel engine was fueled with pentanol/diesel fuel blends (in a range between 10% and 25% of pentanol) and engine performance tests were compared with the use of neat diesel fuel. Based on this study, 25% pentanol/75% diesel fuel blend can be recommended as a diesel fuel substitute if long-term diesel engine tests provide satisfactory results.[7] In this research work investigate that Triglycerides and their derivatives are considered as viable alternatives for diesel fuels. Highly viscous Rice bran oil can be used by blending it with diesel so viscosity of mixture reduced and used as a fuel. To investigate experimentally the performance, exhaust emission and combustion characteristics of a direct injection (DI) diesel engine, typically used in agricultural sector, over the entire load range when fuelled with rice bran oil and diesel fuel blends, RB10 (10% rice bran oil + 90% diesel fuel) to RB50. The performance, emission and combustion parameters of RB20 were found to be very close to neat diesel fuel. No problem was faced at the time of starting the engine and ran smoothly over the range of rice bran oil percent in fuel blend.[8] to study the performance, emission and combustion characteristics of a DI diesel engine using poon oil-based fuels. In the present work, poon oil and poon oil methyl ester are tested as diesel fuels in Neat and blended forms. The blends were prepared with 20% poon oil and 40% poon oil methyl ester separately with standard diesel on a volume basis. On the whole it is concluded that the methyl ester of poon oil and its diesel blends can be chosen as fuel in a diesel engine without any engine modification. The performance of the methyl ester of poon oil and its diesel blends fueled diesel engine was marginally better than that of the conventional diesel engine in terms of exhaust emissions except NO_x emission.[9] The performance, emission and combustion characteristics of a multi fuel variable compression ratio engine fueled with waste cooking oil bio diesel and diesel blends have been investigated and compared with that of standard diesel The experimental results confirm that the BTE, SFC, BP, exhaust gas temperature and mechanical efficiency of variable compression ratio engine, are a function of bio diesel blend, load and compression ratio. For the similar operating conditions, engine performance reduced with increase in bio diesel percentage in the blend and compared with that of standard diesel. However by increasing the compression ratio the engine performance varied and it becomes comparable with that of standard diesel. experimental result also proves that lower and medium percentages of waste cooking oil methyl ester can be substituted for diesel fuel.[10]

Nomenclature	
St.Di	Standard Diesel

WCO(C+P)	Waste cooking Cotton and Palm bio diesel
WCOP	Waste cooking palm bio diesel
WCO	Waste cotton seed bio diesel
CR	Compression Ratio
IP	Indicated power
BP	Brake power
SFC	Specific fuel consumption
BTE	Brake thermal efficiency

The performance, emission and combustion characteristics of a multi fuel variable compression ratio engine fueled with waste cooking oil bio diesel and diesel blends have been investigated and compared with that of standard diesel. The experimental results confirm that the BTE, SFC, BP, exhaust gas temperature and mechanical efficiency of variable compression ratio engine, are a function of bio diesel blend, load and compression ratio. For the similar operating conditions, engine performance reduced with increase in bio diesel percentage in the blend and compared with that of standard diesel. However by increasing the compression ratio the engine performance varied and it becomes comparable with that of standard diesel. experimental result also proves that lower and medium percentages of waste cooking oil methyl ester can be substituted for diesel fuel.[11]

Biodiesel Production

Waste Cotton seed Cooking oils and palm oil are extracted from edible oils and vastly used in hotels and restaurants. It has been reported that these edible oils degrade in quality after repeated use. These oils should be discarded once the concentration of polar compounds reach 25% or higher. These discarded oils are useful for biodiesel production as it can solve the problem of waste handling and can act as an alternative fuel as well. The quality of the produced biodiesel may be better compared to the biodiesel produced from non-edible oils

The transesterification process was used to produce biodiesel from waste cooking oil. Waste cooking oil was heated up to 70°C in a round bottom flask equipped with a reflux condenser, thermometer and magnetic stirrer to drive off moisture and stirred vigorously. Potassium hydroxide (1 wt% of waste cooking oil as a catalyst was dissolved in methanol solution of (6:1M ratio of the waste cooking oil) in a flask, then was added to the round flask and left for to react for 1.5 h. Glycerol was separated from biodiesel using separating funnel and washed using warm water 5% acid. Biodiesel was separated using rotary evaporator at 80°C then dried at 100°C.

Triglyceride Alcohol Alkyl Ester Glycerol

Fig. 1 General Transesterification Reaction Equation

The amount of heat and water increases the hydrolysis of triglycerides and the percent of free fatty acid (FFA) in the oil. The water and FFA content has a negative influence on the transesterification reaction. The WCO price is two to three times cheaper than vegetable oils.

Fig 2 Flow Diagram of Transesterification Process

Experimental test rig

A four-stroke single cylinder diesel engine of technical specifications were summarized in Table that employed for testing. A schematic drawing of the experimental setup including the necessary measuring devices were shown in Fig. 3 An AC generator;4.5 kW maximum power, was directly coupled to determine the engine brake

power where external controllable electric load bank with variable loads was used. The present study was carried out to investigate the performance and exhaust emissions of a diesel engine fuelled with two biodiesel with conventional diesel fuel as a 10 , 20 and Mix of both percentage blend as volume basis of Waste cotton seed oil and waste palm biodiesel blends. The engine had been equipped to measure fuel consumption and engine speed. The engine received air through an air box fitted with an orifice for measuring the air consumption.

In experimental set up start with the ignition starter switch before that the fuel tank filled with blended diesel, for maintained constant engine speed and thermal stabilization that performed the experiment with test result of combustion and performance characteristics of Waste cooking cotton seed extracted biodiesel blended 10%, 20% with diesel in CI engine was performed for five loading conditions (no load, 25%, 50%, 75% and 100% loading condition) at constant engine speed of 1500 rpm. Experiments were performed for compression ratios (CR) of 18 for Diesel and waste cotton seed bio diesel and Waste plam seed oil and equal proportion of miture of both oil at tested conditions, to see the effect of different blending of Waste cotton seed biodiesel (WCOB), Waste palm seed oil and equal proportion of mixture of both oil (i.e 5% each oil in 10 % blended) with 10%, 20% with diesel at 18 CR on performance and emission characteristics. Injection timing was fixed at 23° bTDC (before top dead center) for tested conditions and engine speed was maintained constant at 1500 rpm. Performance and combustion reading was taken after thermal stabilization of engine for each test condition and an average of 50 consecutive thermodynamic cycles were considered for combustion analysis. Experiment were performed in a single cylinder four stroke water cooled Diesel engine And detailed specification in Table 1

Engine and Dynamometer Specifications:

Compression ratio	17
Fuel	Diesel
No.of cylinder	4
Bore Diameter	87.50 mm
Stroke lengh L	110 mm
Connecting road	234 mm
Swept volume	661.45 cc
Cooling	Water
Speed	1700
Rated Power	3.5 kw
Starting	Electric
Dynamometer type	Eddy current dynamometer

Table 1

Fig 3 Experimental Set up

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Thermo physical properties of the biodiesel compared with neat diesel and ASTM D6751 standard are shown in Table 1.

Sample/Properties	Specific Gravity	Density	LCV	HCV	Flash point	Fire point	Kinematic viscosity @40°C	Dynamic viscosity @40°C

Unit		Kg/m ³	Calorie/ gm-°C	Calorie/g m-°C	°C	°C	cSt	cSt
ASTM Standard	D287	D287	D4809	D4809	D93-58T	D93-58T	D445	D445
St.DI	0.816	816	10236	10822	53	56	2.09	1.73
WCO	0.901	901	9667	10253	320	332	8.19	7.3
WCOBD	0.875	875	9901	10487	160	171	4.07	3.56
WPO	0.907	907	9807	10394	290	311	9.2	8.3
WPOBD	0.866	866	10017	10603	155	162	2.89	2.58

Table 1 Thermo Physical Properties of Oils

For experiment used 10%, 20% WCOCB and WCOPB individual and mixture of both biodiesel with equal % blend with Conventional Diesel and Performance and emission test conducted on 1500 RPM and CR 18 and the result carried out are as follows:

A. Emission Graph: Emission Result Compare With 10% Blend Of Wco And Wcop And Wco+Wcop With Diesel At 1500 Rpm And Cr 18 With Load (0,3,6,9,12)Kw

Fig 4 (a, b, c, d) Emission characteristics

Fig 4 (a,b,c,d,e) shows emission characteristics of Diesel, wco10, wcop10 and wco (c+p)10 biodiesel blended in 10 % by volume in mixture of diesel and biodiesel extracted from waste cooking oil of cotton seed oil and palm oil. Fig. 4 show emission of CO₂, CO, HC, NO and Smoke is minimum in case of wco10 and maximum in

case of wco10 in case of all biodiesel. The interesting part is that due to blending of biodiesel emission reduces in comparison of diesel.

B. Performance Graph: Performance Result Compare At 10% Blend Of Wco And Wcop And Wco+Wcop With Diesel At 1500 Rpm And Cr 18 With Load (0,3,6,9,12)Kw

Fig 5 (a,b,c,d,e) Thermal performance

Fig 5 (a, b, c, d, e, f) indicates thermal performance characteristics of Diesel, wco10, wcop10 and wco (c+p)10 biodiesel blended in 10 % by volume in mixture of diesel and biodiesel extracted from waste cooking oil of cotton seed oil and palm oil. Fig 5 (a) and 5(b) show indicated power and indicated thermal efficiency which represent that in case of wco (c+p)10 biodiesel blended in 10 % by volume in mixture of diesel gives better results and at the same time from Fig 5 (c, d, e, f) show that break power, break thermal efficiency, mechanical efficiency and having excellent values in case of wco (c+p)10 biodiesel.

C. EMISSION GRAPH: Emission Result Compare At 20% Blend Of Wco And Wcop And Wco+Wcop With Diesel At 1500 Rpm And Cr 18 With Load (0,3,6,9,12)Kw

Fig 6 (a,b,c,d,e) shows emission characteristics of Diesel, wco20, wcop20 and wco (c+p) 20 biodiesel blended in 20 % by volume in mixture of diesel and biodiesel extracted from waste cooking oil of cotton seed oil and palm oil. Fig. 6 show emission of CO₂ is reduces up to 50 % load rise and there afterwards increment CO₂ in

emission values and rising trend with increment in loads is observed in case of in case of wco20 but emission values are lower compare to wcop20 and wco (c+p) 20.

Fig.6 (a,b,c,d,e) Emission characteristics

D. PERFORMANCE GRAPH: PERFORMANCE RESULT COMPARE AT 20% BLEND OF WCO AND WCO+WCOP AND WCO+WCOP WITH DIESEL AT 1500 RPM AND CR 18 with Load (0,3,6,9,12)KW

Fig 7 (a, b, c, d, e, f) Performance characteristics

Fig 7 (a, b, c, d, e, f) indicates thermal performance characteristics of Diesel, wco10, wco20 and wco(c+p)10 biodiesel blended in 10% by volume in mixture of diesel and biodiesel extracted from waste cooking oil of cotton seed oil and palm oil. Fig 7 (a) and 7(b) show indicated power and indicated thermal efficiency which represent that in case of wco(c+p)10 biodiesel blended in 10% by volume in mixture of diesel gives better results and at the same time from Fig 7 (c, d, e, f) show that break power, break thermal efficiency, mechanical efficiency and having excellent values in case of wco(c+p)20 biodiesel. Compare to wco(c+p)10 in case of wco(c+p)20 more satisfactory results can be seen.

CONCLUSION

India is bestowed with abundant resources, which are sustainable and eco-friendly options to produce biofuels. Therefore its production and consumption should be encouraged in every way possible it is the fuel of the 21st century in many possible ways as use WCO Biodiesel in a single-cylinder diesel engine. Performance and exhaust emissions at different motor loads perform better, It is promising to use bio-diesel as fossil diesel substitute fuel of 21st century. The biodiesel boom, however, has raised concerns about food shortages worldwide and may lead to a food crisis. The shift to alternative, non-food feedstocks including waste cooking oils is currently a major focus to avoid using food resources for fuel.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. K. Nayak and B. P. Pattanaik, "Experimental investigation on performance and emission characteristics of a diesel engine fuelled with mahua biodiesel using additive," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 54, pp. 569–579, 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.egypro.2014.07.298.
- [2] K. A. Abed, A. K. El Morsi, M. M. Sayed, A. A. E. Shaib, and M. S. Gad, "Effect of waste cooking-oil biodiesel on performance and exhaust emissions of a diesel engine," *Egypt. J. Pet.*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 985–989, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.ejpe.2018.02.008.
- [3] M. A. Kalam, H. H. Masjuki, M. H. Jayed, and A. M. Liaquat, "Emission and performance characteristics of an indirect ignition diesel engine fuelled with waste cooking oil," *Energy*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 397–402, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2010.10.026.

-
- [4] A. Atmanli, E. Ileri, and N. Yilmaz, "Optimization of diesel-butanol-vegetable oil blend ratios based on engine operating parameters," *Energy*, vol. 96, no. 2016, pp. 569–580, 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2015.12.091.
- [5] S. R. Amini-Niaki and A. Ghazanfari, "Comparison of fuel and emission properties of petro diesel and sunflower biodiesel prepared by optimized production variables," *Fuel*, vol. 109, pp. 384–388, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.fuel.2012.11.012.
- [6] B. S. Chauhan, N. Kumar, and H. M. Cho, "A study on the performance and emission of a diesel engine fueled with *Jatropha* biodiesel oil and its blends," *Energy*, vol. 37, no. 1, pp. 616–622, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2011.10.043.
- [7] J. Campos-Fernandez, J. M. Arnal, J. Gomez, N. Lacalle, and M. P. Dorado, "Performance tests of a diesel engine fueled with pentanol/diesel fuel blends," *Fuel*, vol. 107, pp. 866–872, 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.fuel.2013.01.066.
- [8] B. K. Venkanna and C. Venkataraman Reddy, "Performance, emission, and combustion characteristics of a diesel engine running on blends of honne oil and diesel fuel," *Int. J. Green Energy*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 728–736, 2015, doi: 10.1080/15435075.2011.653850.
- [9] P. K. Devan and N. V. Mahalakshmi, "Study of the performance, emission and combustion characteristics of a diesel engine using poon oil-based fuels," *Fuel Process. Technol.*, vol. 90, no. 4, pp. 513–519, 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.fuproc.2009.01.009.
- [10] K. Muralidharan, D. Vasudevan, and K. N. Sheeba, "Performance, emission and combustion characteristics of biodiesel fuelled variable compression ratio engine," *Energy*, vol. 36, no. 8, pp. 5385–5393, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2011.06.050.
- [11] K. Muralidharan and D. Vasudevan, "Performance, emission and combustion characteristics of a variable compression ratio engine using methyl esters of waste cooking oil and diesel blends," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 88, no. 11, pp. 3959–3968, 2011, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2011.04.014.

AUTHOR DETAILS:**¹PRAKASHKUMAR PRAJAPATI AND ²SADANAND NAMJOSHI**¹Research Scholar Mechanical Engineering Department, Madhav University, Abu road, India²Mechanical Engineering Department, Madhav University, Abu road, India